

data. Isotope analyses of cereals and soils were included in the last years to evaluate isotopes from archaeobotanical material as possible markers for slash-and-burn in the past. We are also investigating the fate of charcoal in the soil to allow comparisons with Neolithic black soils.

565 PLANT AND ANIMAL USE IN LATE MEDIEVAL AND MODERN RELIGIOUS CONTEXTS IN CENTRAL ITALY

Abstract theme: 1. The Material Record: Current Trends and Future Directions

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Abstract format: Poster

Excavations carried out between 1996 and 2016 in Latium and Umbria (Central Italy) allowed the recovery of faunal and, sometimes, plant remains from religious contexts spanning from the 13th to the 17th century. The analysis of these organic materials, as well as their comparison, allowed us to investigate how these resources were used not only by the monastic communities but also by laypeople who lived in and around these religious complexes. The examined assemblages represent, in most cases, food waste but also include plants and animals employed for other purposes. The diet was, of course, influenced by religious rules; however, it differed, for example, according to the monastic order, the chronological period, the local availability of resources, and the social status. In this sense, noteworthy is the retrieval of *Cucurbita* sp. (pumpkin) seeds and a *Cavia porcellus* (Guinea pig) pelvis in Early Modern contexts from the Santi Quattro Coronati complex (Rome), products imported from the newly discovered Americas, thus available only to the elite.

566 GEOPHYSICAL AND GEOCHEMICAL PROSPECTION AT THE RINGFORTS ON ÖLAND, SWEDEN

Abstract theme: 2. Archaeological Sciences, Humanities and the Digital era: Bridging the Gaps

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Abstract format: Poster

The use of the ringforts on Öland, dated to the migration period (200-800 CE) have long been debated with many different interpretations, such as defence systems, meeting places, cult places and that it reflected turbulent times. One method to quickly gain more information about the ringforts is different archaeological prospection methods, e.g. LiDAR, ground-penetrating radar, magnetometry and soil samples. The project CrisConClimate aims to study archaeological change related to crisis, conflict, and climate with the ringforts on Öland as a case study. A wide range of archaeological research methods will be used and one of them is archaeological prospection that will be carried out as an initial step before turning to other materials and methods. The aim of the prospection is to gain information about the spatial layout, structures, wells, defence systems and other features of interest that can be used in the forthcoming research. The methods that have been used are LiDAR, ground-penetrating radar and pXRF element analysis of soil samples. The LiDAR data gave high resolution pictures of the ringforts, something that was not available before and will help the interpretation of the sites. The result from the ground-penetrating radar survey was more difficult to interpret but could confirm that most of the archaeological structures have been removed, maybe due to ploughing. The soil samples showed the mineral content of the ringforts that was compared to divide them into different types and indicate different activity areas. All these methods show that archaeological prospection is highly relevant and can give a lot of new information about archaeological sites without having to damage the sites and do archaeological excavations, something that is not possible to do over such large areas.